

ANALYSIS OF THE PHENOMENON OF “SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS” IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation. This article analyzes the phenomenon of “social consciousness” in preschool children. It should be noted that self-awareness is not built over a person from the outside, but is part of it; therefore, it does not have a separate, independent path of development from the development of a person, self-awareness enters this process of personality development as a real subject as its moment, side, component. It is stated that self - awareness is the line of value that constitutes the system of personal meanings that make up the individual existence of the individual.

Keywords: psyche, preschool age, character, component, thought, personality, cognition.

Introduction

In Psychological Science, there are different opinions about the components that make up the structure of self-awareness. The structure of the self-consciousness of a person is a set of stable connections in the field of value orientations and the human worldview, ensuring its unique integrity and originality in relation to himself . A person's self-awareness is such an understandable unit that he finds expression in each of the following five links: the correct name is the first link in the structure of self-awareness. Name-the personal name of the person who was given to him at birth in the first place; a sign that allows you to classify a person into a certain social stratum, ethnic group, gender, rather than social relations. The name has a psychological meaning: it becomes the first crystal of personality, around which the very essence of a person is formed. Thanks to the noun and the pronoun "I", the child learns to distinguish himself as a person. Recognition claim-the person's representation of their rights is respected by the people. From an early age, the child determines that all his actions are divided into "good" and "bad".

Since every good thing is emotionally rewarded, the child has a desire to be good, the development of an active desire to learn what is approved by the people around him begins. Gender identity - includes the value orientation of a person to his gender as a social role, sexual power, and sexual behavior, and also includes psychological recognition of his identity with gender from a physical, social, and psychological point of view. Gender identity is the unity of the self-

realization, motives of behavior, actions of a person who classifies himself as a particular gender and assumes the corresponding gender role established by traditions. Psychological time of a person-individual experience its physical and spiritual transformation over time, expressed by the past, present and future in the segment of the objective time of life.

The social space of a person is a person whose conditions for development and existence include him psychologically in the sphere of rights and duties. The conditions are as follows: 1) the place where the life of a person takes place; 2) the style and content of communication in the context of the culture to which the person belongs; 3) the internal position of a person as a holistic, historically conditioned phenomenon in the history of his ethnic group, culture. There are other approaches to the structure of self-awareness. S.L. According to Rubinstein, personality does not fall into the level of consciousness and self-awareness, but it is impossible without them. Personal self-awareness includes a sense of self-awareness, a special psychological structure - "I", the level of self-esteem and claims.

Awareness of oneself ensures the integrity of the individual, opposes his bifurcation. The person subjectively acts as his "I" for the person. The totality of mental phenomena reflecting his "I" personality received the name "I - concept" in psychology, which includes the following components: Cognitive - the image of "I", an idea of one's own qualities, abilities, capabilities; emotional - self-attitude, self - esteem, pride evaluative-volitional-self-esteem, self-regulation. Self-awareness is formed in the process of mental development of the child. It distinguishes the "crystal of personality" in self-awareness. The basis of the "crystal " is the correct name (which is distinguished by body individuality) and social recognition, which the child receives first from a close, and then from a more distant social environment. When discussing the problem of the formation of the image of a person "I", several successive stages can be distinguished: self-awareness, the idea of a body scheme, self-perception, self-esteem, the choice of "I" as an internal subject. The lower levels of the structure of the image of "I", with the help of special techniques, naturally, do not fully reflect self-realization, but can only be characterized by its individual elements. The number of such studies is quite large. The study of the child's self-consciousness is very difficult, first of all, from the point of view of the methodological arsenal. By self-description, it is possible to study the "I-concept" itself as a reflex assessment of oneself and one's own capabilities only when a sufficiently high level of "I" formation is reached. All researchers attribute the development of the

foundations of self-awareness to early (and some even infancy) age. It occurs in the process of active movement of the child, which is largely determined by his internal state. The child no longer only knows his name, he "discovers himself" as a separate person. Arbitrary acquisition of one's own body begins. The result is the emergence of targeted actions and actions. In the process of Motor development, general body coordination appears. At an early age, primary ideas about the body scheme are usually formed, and self-awareness is relatively differentiated. A normally developing child is able to localize body sensations in the middle of the second year of life, in a maximum of two years.

This confirms that the scheme of the body is formed. Earlier (in a year and a half) he begins to recognize himself in the mirror, and then in photographs, which indicates the main differentiation of "I" and "not me". The study of children deprived of motherhood showed that at this age they often do not recognize themselves in the mirror and, moreover, in photographs. In addition to determining the delay in highlighting one's own "I", this fact can be explained by the fact that the experience of such a type of action is significantly less. It has been proven that the age conditions for the emergence of the possibility of self-recognition depend on the presence of individual interaction with adults.

The possibility of localizing body sensations can be determined mainly if the child has speech. In this case, it can not only stretch the arm or leg at the request of an adult, show different parts of the body (this is usually available to children of the second year of life), but also answer the question of what hurts. uni (although this technique is very unreliable due to imitation of children, often copying adult complaints). The delay in speech development significantly complicates the assessment of the formation of this possibility.

Difficulties in learning young children leave many aspects of the early stages of the formation of self-awareness open. Guskova and M.G. Elagina (1987) showed that already at this age, motivational ideas and "pride in achievements" appear in children. This indicates the beginning of the formation of the " i " system. However, it should be repeated that the appearance of these most important personality neoplasms is predetermined by the interaction of the child and adults. The performance of one action for another appears in the child in the process of communication, under the influence of upbringing and under the requirements of adults, and only then in those conditions that are required by the objective objective conditions of his activity. Thus, in the process of communication, under the influence of adults, the subordination of motives begins to form, which determines the ability to regulate one's own behavior. The

emergence of motivating ideas determines the initial stage in the development of volitional behavior. In connection with the formation of sufficiently stable ideas, feelings and desires, the baby is associated with what he remembers, although he does not see them in front of him at the moment. The child will be less dependent on the current situation. It is from this period that he begins to "wound" his behavior in accordance with his desires and ideas. According to many psychologists, knowing and discovering one's own "I" is the dominant line of development during this period. At the same time, this is the beginning of a long process of self-realization. Therefore, it is probably more correct to say that at an early age, the necessary conditions are formed for the appearance of elements of self-awareness, which are usually open to experimental study.

Rubinstein, who believed that self-awareness is primary in relation to consciousness, believes that the self-awareness of a preschool child is a stage in the development of consciousness. It is prepared by the appearance of speech, the growth of independence, as well as changes associated with these processes in relations with others. Let's turn to the analysis of information about the development of self-awareness in preschool children. Leantiev, D.B. Elkanin and L.S. Vygotsky "postponed the emergence of clearly expressed signs of self-awareness to the preschool period." At the same time: "self-esteem, that is, knowledge of one's own qualities and the disclosure of one's own experience for oneself, means self-awareness, which by the end of preschool age is formed as its main neoplasm (it should be noted that neither self-esteem nor internal experiences have yet been generalized by the child, their generalization is the main.

Modern researchers are not so strict in assessing the potential of a preschool child for self-knowledge and assimilation of their behavior. A.L. Wenger noted that in preschool age, the main image of "I" appears, which is inextricably linked with his actions and knowledge of the situation in which they are carried out. By the age of 7, the child will have differences between "I am real" and "I am ideal." The subjective principle implies a holistic feeling of oneself as a source of one's own will, experience and activity. It can be seen as a center of self-awareness.

The principle of the object - ideas about everything that the pronoun "my" can apply - is the edge of self-realization. The subjective principle gives rise to different forms of interference with the other (empathy, cooperation). Self-esteem and self-imagination, according to the author, are associated with an objective principle. Self-esteem is an attitude towards specific qualities, the image of "I" is an idea of one's own capabilities, abilities, place among others. As

you can see, there are some differences in these definitions from those that we have given earlier. With normal mental development in the middle of preschool age, peripheral structures and object components of the image of the "I" are formed.

By the old preschool age, the subjective component of self-awareness increases, it goes beyond the properties of the object and becomes open. The child will be able to give a moral assessment of the actions of others, to understand their experiences. In the literature there are some contradictions in this regard, since the authors presented above believe that the moral considerations of the child belong not to the "individual self", but to the "social" one. L.S. Vygotsky believes that the possibility of moral reasoning is the result of the development of self-awareness associated with the "loss of speed" inherent in a 7-year-old child and is a reflection of the perception of the "ideal" form, which, as mentioned above, is presented to the child by an adult. In other words, it can be interpreted as evidence of the separation of "I-real" and "I-ideal". The emergence of moral considerations is assessed by researchers as an indirect indicator of the differentiation of self-awareness, since they indicate the contradiction of the "good"- "bad" image of self - awareness and the desire to look better in the eyes of people. However, the known "norm" is often distinguished from the real behavior of the child.

Therefore, moral considerations can be considered as the result of mastering (but not mastering) the norms of social behavior. It should be noted that for the psychology of the individual and his development is a central problem of Will and arbitrariness, which covers a wide range of various phenomena: actions according to the instructions, perseverance and independence in achieving goals, subordination of motives, adherence to rules; goal setting, voluntary actions, moral choice, mediated by cognitive processes. It can also be noted that preschool age characterizes the child's self-consciousness as an understanding of the motives and goals of behavior and the means of achieving them, since knowledge of the means of achieving the goal leads to the establishment of a hierarchy of motives. It should be noted that indirect indicators of the establishment of such a hierarchy are the child's ability to behave in accordance with the rules of relations established in a preschool educational institution, as well as compliance with the instructions of an adult in group activities. Of course, the success of completing tasks depends not only on the arbitrariness of behavior, but also on other factors.

In addition, behavior can be stereotyped and unconscious. In this case, there is a lack of attention to one's own actions and an underdevelopment of the motivational-volitional sphere of the child. The fulfillment of the rules is alienated, binding, depending on the situation, and is not recognized as an independent act of the individual. According to the author, such an action cannot be considered arbitrary. From this one can conclude about the importance of the formation of self-awareness for the development of "real" arbitrariness. A different, more detailed structure of the child's self-consciousness can be expressed as follows: "self-awareness is the value orientation that forms the system of personal meanings that make up the individual existence of the individual. In art, a system of personal meanings is established.

Conclusion

"Self-esteem, that is, knowledge of one's own qualities and the disclosure of one's own experience for oneself, means self-awareness, which by the end of preschool age is formed as its main neoplasm (it should be noted that neither self-esteem nor internal experiences have yet been generalized by the child, the generalization of which is the main content of the transition. Therefore, moral considerations can be considered as the result of mastering (but not mastering) the norms of social behavior. It should be noted that for the psychology of the individual and his development is a central problem of Will and arbitrariness, which covers a wide range of various phenomena: actions according to the instructions, perseverance and independence in achieving goals, subordination of motives, adherence to rules; goal setting, voluntary actions, moral choice, mediated by cognitive processes. It can also be noted that preschool age characterizes the child's self-consciousness as an understanding of the motives and goals of behavior and the means of achieving them, since knowledge of the means of achieving the goal leads to the establishment of a hierarchy of motives. It should be noted that indirect indicators of the establishment of such a hierarchy are the child's ability to behave in accordance with the rules of relations established in a preschool educational institution, as well as compliance with the instructions of an adult in group activities.

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